

Critical Impurity Densities in the Mott Metal-Insulator Transition, Obtained in Three n(p) - Type Degenerate GaAs_{1-x}Te_x(Sb_x, P_x)-Crystalline Alloys

Huynh Van Cong ✉

Université de Perpignan Via Domitia, Laboratoire de Mathématiques et Physique (LAMPS), EA 4217, Département de Physique, 52, Avenue Paul Alduy, F-66 860 Perpignan, France

ABSTRACT:

By basing on the same physical model and treatment method, as used in our recent works [1, 2, 3, 4, 5], we will investigate the critical impurity densities in the metal-insulator transition (MIT), obtained in three n(p)-type degenerate [GaAs_{1-x}Te_x, GaAs_{1-x}Sb_x, GaAs_{1-x}P_x]- crystalline alloys, $0 \leq x \leq 1$, being due to the effects of the size of donor (acceptor) d(a)-radius, $r_{d(a)}$, the x-Ge concentration, and finally the high d(a)-density, N, assuming that all the impurities are ionized even at T=0 K. In such n(p)-type degenerate crystalline alloys, we will determine:

(i)-the critical impurity densities $N_{CDn(CDp)}(r_{d(a)}, x)$ in the MIT, as that given in Eq. (10), by using an empirical Mott parameter $M_{n(p)} = 0.25$, and

(ii)-the density of electrons (holes) localized in the exponential conduction (valence)-band tails (EBT), $N_{CDn(CDp)}^{EBT}(r_{d(a)}, x)$, as that given in Eq. (26), by using the empirical Heisenberg parameter, $\mathcal{H}_{n(p)} = 0.47137$, as given in Eq. (17), according to: for given $r_{d(a)}$ and x, $N_{CDn(CDp)}^{EBT}(r_{d(a)}, x) \cong N_{CDn(CDp)}(r_{d(a)}, x)$, with a precision of the order of 2.92×10^{-7} , as observed in Tables 1, 2 and 3.

In other words, such the critical d(a)-density $N_{CDn(NDp)}(r_{d(a)}, x)$, is just the density of electrons (holes) localized in the EBT, $N_{CDn(CDp)}^{EBT}(r_{d(a)}, x)$, respectively.

Keywords: [GaAs_{1-x}Te_x, GaAs_{1-x}Sb_x, GaAs_{1-x}P_x]-crystalline alloys, critical impurity density in the MIT.

Suggested Citation: H. Van Cong, " Critical Impurity Densities in the Mott Metal-Insulator Transition, Obtained in Three n(p) - Type Degenerate GaAs_{1-x}Te_x(Sb_x, P_x)-Crystalline Alloys," *Eur. J. Appl. Sc. Eng. Technol.*, vol. 2(1), pp. 34-49, Jan-Feb 2024. DOI: [10.59324/ejaset.2024.2\(1\).05](https://doi.org/10.59324/ejaset.2024.2(1).05)

INTRODUCTION

By basing on the same intrinsic energy-band-structure parameters [1, 2, 3], physical model and treatment method, as used in our recent works [4, 5], and also other works [6, 7, 8, 9, 10, 11], we will investigate the critical impurity density in the metal-insulator transition (MIT), obtained in three n(p)-type degenerate X(x)- crystalline alloys, $X(x) \equiv [GaAs_{1-x}Te_x, GaAs_{1-x}Sb_x, GaAs_{1-x}P_x]$, $0 \leq x \leq 1$, being due to the effects of the size of donor (acceptor) d(a)-radius, $r_{d(a)}$, the x-(Te, Sb, P) concentration, and finally the high d(a)-density, N, assuming that all the impurities are ionized even at T=0 K. In such n(p)-type degenerate crystalline alloys, we will determine:

(i)-the critical impurity densities $N_{CDn(CDp)}(r_{d(a)}, x)$ in the MIT, as that given in Eq. (10), by using an empirical Mott parameter $M_{n(p)} = 0.25$, and

(ii)-the density of electrons (holes) localized in the exponential conduction(valence)-band tails (EBT), $N_{CDn(CDp)}^{EBT}(r_{d(a)}, x)$, as that given in Eq. (26), by using the empirical Heisenberg parameter, $\mathcal{H}_{n(p)} = 0.47137$, as that given in Eq. (17), according to: for given $r_{d(a)}$ and x , $N_{CDn(CDp)}^{EBT}(r_{d(a)}, x) \cong N_{CDn(CDp)}(r_{d(a)}, x)$, with a precision of the order of 2.92×10^{-7} , as seen in Tables 1, 2 and 3.

In other words, such the critical d(a)-density $N_{CDn(NDP)}(r_{d(a)}, x)$, is just the density of electrons (holes) localized in the EBT, $N_{CDn(CDp)}^{EBT}(r_{d(a)}, x)$, respectively.

In the following, we will determine those functions: $N_{CDn(CDp)}(r_{d(a)}, x)$ and $N_{CDn(CDp)}^{EBT}(r_{d(a)}, x)$.

CRITICAL DENSITY IN THE MIT, $N_{CDn(CDp)}(r_{d(a)}, x)$

Such the critical impurity density $N_{CDn(CDp)}(r_{d(a)}, x)$, expressed as a function of $r_{d(a)}$ and x , is determined as follows.

Effect of x-(Te, Sb, P) concentration

Here, the values of the intrinsic energy-band-structure parameters, such as [1-11]: the effective average number of equivalent conduction (valence)-band edges $g_{c(v)}(x)$, the unperturbed relative effective electron (hole) mass in conduction (valence) bands $m_{c(v)}(x)/m_0$, m_0 being the electron rest mass, the reduced effective mass $m_r(x)/m_0$, the unperturbed relative dielectric static constant $\epsilon_0(x)$, the effective donor (acceptor)-ionization energy $E_{do(ao)}(x)$, and the isothermal bulk modulus $B_{do(ao)}(x) \equiv \frac{E_{do(ao)}(x)}{(4\pi/3) \times (r_{do(ao)})^3}$, at $r_{d(a)} = r_{do(ao)} \equiv r_{As(Ga)} = 0.118 \text{ nm}$ (0.126 nm), are given respectively in the following.

$$g_c(x) = 1 \times x + 1 \times (1 - x) = 1, \quad g_v(x) = 1 \times x + 1 \times (1 - x) = 1, \quad (1)$$

$$m_c(x)/m_0 = 0.209 \times x + 0.066 \times (1 - x), \quad m_v(x)/m_0 = 0.4 \times x + 0.291 \times (1 - x), \quad \text{for GaAs}_{1-x}\text{Te}_x, \\ m_c(x)/m_0 = 0.047 \times x + 0.066 \times (1 - x), \quad m_v(x)/m_0 = 0.3 \times x + 0.291 \times (1 - x), \quad \text{for GaAs}_{1-x}\text{Sb}_x, \\ m_c(x)/m_0 = 0.13 \times x + 0.066 \times (1 - x), \quad m_v(x)/m_0 = 0.5 \times x + 0.291 \times (1 - x), \quad \text{for GaAs}_{1-x}\text{P}_x, \quad (2)$$

$$\epsilon_0(x) = 12.3 \times x + 13.13 \times (1 - x), \quad \text{for GaAs}_{1-x}\text{Te}_x,$$

$$\epsilon_0(x) = 15.69 \times x + 13.13 \times (1 - x), \quad \text{for GaAs}_{1-x}\text{Sb}_x,$$

$$\epsilon_0(x) = 11.1 \times x + 13.13 \times (1 - x), \quad \text{for GaAs}_{1-x}\text{P}_x, \quad (3)$$

$$E_{go}(x) \text{ in eV} = 1.796 \times x + 1.52 \times (1 - x), \quad \text{for GaAs}_{1-x}\text{Te}_x,$$

$$E_{go}(x) \text{ in eV} = 0.81 \times x + 1.52 \times (1 - x), \quad \text{for GaAs}_{1-x}\text{Sb}_x,$$

$$E_{go}(x) \text{ in eV} = 1.796 \times x + 1.52 \times (1 - x), \quad \text{for GaAs}_{1-x}\text{P}_x, \quad (4)$$

$$E_{do(ao)}(x) = \frac{13600 \times [m_{c(v)}(x)/m_0]}{[\epsilon_0(x)]^2} \text{ meV, and} \quad (5)$$

$$B_{do(ao)}(x) \equiv \frac{E_{do(ao)}(x)}{(4\pi/3) \times (r_{do(ao)})^3}. \quad (6)$$

Effects of impurity size, with a given x

Here, one shows that the effects of the size of donor (acceptor) d(a)-radius, $r_{d(a)}$, and the x-concentration strongly affects the changes in all the energy-band-structure parameters, which can be represented by the effective relative static dielectric constant $\epsilon(r_{d(a)}, x)$, in the following.

At $r_{d(a)} = r_{do(ao)}$, the needed boundary conditions are found to be, for the impurity-atom volume $V = (4\pi/3) \times (r_{d(a)})^3$, $V_{do(ao)} = (4\pi/3) \times (r_{do(ao)})^3$, for the pressure p , as: $p_0 = 0$, and for the

deformation potential energy (or the strain energy) σ , as: $\sigma_0 = 0$. Further, the two important equations [4, 5, 11], used to determine the σ -variation: $\Delta\sigma \equiv \sigma - \sigma_0 = \sigma$, are defined by: $\frac{dp}{dV} = -\frac{B}{V}$ and $p = -\frac{d\sigma}{dV}$. giving: $\frac{d}{dV}\left(\frac{d\sigma}{dV}\right) = \frac{B}{V}$. Then, by an integration, one gets:

$$\begin{aligned} [\Delta\sigma(r_{d(a)}, x)]_{n(p)} &= B_{do(ao)}(x) \times (V - V_{do(ao)}) \times \ln\left(\frac{V}{V_{do(ao)}}\right) = \\ &= E_{do(ao)}(x) \times \left[\left(\frac{r_{d(a)}}{r_{do(ao)}}\right)^3 - 1 \right] \times \ln\left(\frac{r_{d(a)}}{r_{do(ao)}}\right)^3 \geq 0. \end{aligned} \quad (7a)$$

Furthermore, we also shown that, as $r_{d(a)} > r_{do(ao)}$ ($r_{d(a)} < r_{do(ao)}$), the compression (dilatation) gives rise to: the increase (the decrease) in the energy gap $E_{gno(gp)}(r_{d(a)}, x)$, and in the effective donor (acceptor)-ionization energy $E_{d(a)}(r_{d(a)}, x)$ in absolute values, being obtained from the effective Bohr model, and then such the compression (dilatation) is represented respectively by: $\pm [\Delta\sigma(r_{d(a)}, x)]_{n(p)}$,

$$\begin{aligned} E_{gno(gp)}(r_{d(a)}, x) - E_{go}(x) &= E_{d(a)}(r_{d(a)}, x) - E_{do(ao)}(x) = E_{do(ao)}(x) \times \left[\left(\frac{\epsilon_0(x)}{\epsilon(r_{d(a)})}\right)^2 - 1 \right] = \\ &= + [\Delta\sigma(r_{d(a)}, x)]_{n(p)}, \end{aligned}$$

for $r_{d(a)} \geq r_{do(ao)}$, and for $r_{d(a)} \leq r_{do(ao)}$,

$$\begin{aligned} E_{gno(gp)}(r_{d(a)}, x) - E_{go}(x) &= E_{d(a)}(r_{d(a)}, x) - E_{do(ao)}(x) = E_{do(ao)}(x) \times \left[\left(\frac{\epsilon_0(x)}{\epsilon(r_{d(a)})}\right)^2 - 1 \right] = \\ &= - [\Delta\sigma(r_{d(a)}, x)]_{n(p)}. \end{aligned} \quad (7b)$$

Therefore, from above Equations (7a) and (7b), one obtains the expressions for relative dielectric constant $\epsilon(r_{d(a)}, x)$ and energy band gap $E_{gn(gp)}(r_{d(a)}, x)$, as:

(i)-for $r_{d(a)} \geq r_{do(ao)}$, since $\epsilon(r_{d(a)}, x) = \frac{\epsilon_0(x)}{\sqrt{1 + \left[\left(\frac{r_{d(a)}}{r_{do(ao)}}\right)^3 - 1\right] \times \ln\left(\frac{r_{d(a)}}{r_{do(ao)}}\right)^3}} \leq \epsilon_0(x)$,

$$\begin{aligned} E_{gno(gp)}(r_{d(a)}, x) - E_{go}(x) &= E_{d(a)}(r_{d(a)}, x) - E_{do(ao)}(x) = E_{do(ao)}(x) \times \left[\left(\frac{r_{d(a)}}{r_{do(ao)}}\right)^3 - 1 \right] \times \\ &\times \ln\left(\frac{r_{d(a)}}{r_{do(ao)}}\right)^3 \geq 0, \end{aligned} \quad (8a)$$

according to the increase in both $E_{gn(gp)}(r_{d(a)}, x)$ and $E_{d(a)}(r_{d(a)}, x)$, for a given x , and

(ii)-for $r_{d(a)} \leq r_{do(ao)}$, since $\epsilon(r_{d(a)}, x) = \frac{\epsilon_0(x)}{\sqrt{1 - \left[\left(\frac{r_{d(a)}}{r_{do(ao)}}\right)^3 - 1\right] \times \ln\left(\frac{r_{d(a)}}{r_{do(ao)}}\right)^3}} \geq \epsilon_0(x)$, with a condition, given by:

$$\left[\left(\frac{r_{d(a)}}{r_{do(ao)}}\right)^3 - 1 \right] \times \ln\left(\frac{r_{d(a)}}{r_{do(ao)}}\right)^3 < 1,$$

$$E_{\text{gno(gp0)}}(r_{d(a)}, x) - E_{\text{go}}(x) = E_{d(a)}(r_{d(a)}, x) - E_{\text{do(ao)}}(x) = -E_{\text{do(ao)}}(x) \times \left[\left(\frac{r_{d(a)}}{r_{\text{do(ao)}}} \right)^3 - 1 \right] \times \times \ln \left(\frac{r_{d(a)}}{r_{\text{do(ao)}}} \right)^3 \leq 0, \quad (8.b)$$

corresponding to the decrease in both $E_{\text{gn(gp)}}(r_{d(a)}, x)$ and $E_{d(a)}(r_{d(a)}, x)$, for a given x .

Furthermore, the effective Bohr radius $a_{\text{Bn(Bp)}}(r_{d(a)})$ is defined by:

$$a_{\text{Bn(Bp)}}(r_{d(a)}, x) \equiv \frac{\varepsilon(r_{d(a)}, x) \times \hbar^2}{m_{c(v)}(x) \times q^2} = 0.53 \times 10^{-8} \text{ cm} \times \frac{\varepsilon(r_{d(a)}, x)}{m_{c(v)}(x)/m_0}, \quad (9)$$

where $-q$ is the electron charge.

Then, the critical donor (acceptor)-density in the MIT, $N_{\text{CDn(NDp)}}(r_{d(a)}, x)$, is determined, using an empirical Mott parameter, $M_{n(p)}$, as:

$$N_{\text{CDn(CDp)}}(r_{d(a)}, x)^{1/3} \times a_{\text{Bn(Bp)}}(r_{d(a)}, x) = M_{n(p)} = 0.25, \quad (10)$$

In the following, these obtained numerical results can also be justified by calculating the numerical results of the density of electrons (holes) localized in exponential conduction (valence)-band (EBT) tails, $N_{\text{CDn(CDp)}}^{\text{EBT}}(r_{d(a)}, x)$.

$N_{\text{CDn(CDp)}}^{\text{EBT}}(r_{d(a)}, x)$ - EXPRESSION

In order to determine $N_{\text{CDn(CDp)}}^{\text{EBT}}(r_{d(a)}, x)$, we first present our physical model and also our mathematical methods.

Physical model

In $n(p)$ -type degenerate $X(x)$ -crystalline alloys, $X(x) \equiv [\text{GaAs}_{1-x}\text{Te}_x, \text{GaAs}_{1-x}\text{Sb}_x, \text{GaAs}_{1-x}\text{P}_x]$, if denoting the Fermi wave number by: $k_{\text{Fn(Fp)}}(N, x) \equiv (3\pi^2 N / g_{c(v)}(x))^{1/3}$, the effective reduced Wigner-Seitz radius $r_{\text{sn(sp)}}$, characteristic of interactions, is defined by:

$$r_{\text{sn(sp)}}(N, r_{d(a)}, x) \equiv \left(\frac{3g_{c(v)}(x)}{4\pi N} \right)^{1/3} \times \frac{1}{a_{\text{Bn(Bp)}}(r_{d(a)}, x)} = 1.1723 \times 10^8 \times \times \left(\frac{g_{c(v)}(x)}{N} \right)^{1/3} \times \frac{m_{c(v)}(x)/m_0}{\varepsilon(r_{d(a)}, x)} \quad (11)$$

So, the ratio of the inverse effective screening length $k_{\text{sn(sp)}}$ to Fermi wave number $k_{\text{Fn(kp)}}$ at 0 K is defined by:

$$R_{\text{sn(sp)}}(N, r_{\text{d(a)}, X}) \equiv \frac{k_{\text{sn(sp)}}}{k_{\text{Fn(Fp)}}} = \frac{k_{\text{Fn(Fp)}}^{-1}}{k_{\text{sn(sp)}}^{-1}} = R_{\text{snWS(spWS)}} + \\ + [R_{\text{snTF(spTF)}} - R_{\text{snWS(spWS)}}] e^{-r_{\text{sn(sp)}}} < 1. \quad (12)$$

These ratios, $R_{\text{snTF(spTF)}}$ and $R_{\text{snWS(spWS)}}$, are determined in following Equations (13, 14).

First, for $N \gg N_{\text{CDn(NDp)}}(r_{\text{d(a)}, X})$, according to the Thomas-Fermi (TF)-approximation, the ratio $R_{\text{snTF(spTF)}}$ is reduced to

$$R_{\text{snTF(spTF)}}(N, r_{\text{d(a)}, X}) \equiv \frac{k_{\text{snTF(spTF)}}}{k_{\text{Fn(Fp)}}} = \frac{k_{\text{Fn(Fp)}}^{-1}}{k_{\text{snTF(spTF)}}^{-1}} = \sqrt{\frac{4\gamma r_{\text{sn(sp)}}(N, r_{\text{d(a)}, X})}{\pi}} \ll 1, \quad (13)$$

being proportional to $N^{-1/6}$.

Secondly, $N < N_{\text{CDn(NDp)}}(r_{\text{d(a)}, X})$, according to the Wigner-Seitz (WS)-approximation, the ratio $R_{\text{snWS(spWS)}}$ is reduced to [4, 5]:

$$R_{\text{snWS(spWS)}}(N, r_{\text{d(a)}, X}) \equiv \frac{k_{\text{snWS(spWS)}}}{k_{\text{Fn(Fp)}}} = \left(\frac{3}{2\pi} - \gamma \frac{d[r_{\text{sn(sp)}}^2 \times E_{\text{CE}}]}{dr_{\text{sn(sp)}}} \right) \times 0.5, \quad (14)$$

where $E_{\text{CE}}(N, r_{\text{d(a)}, X})$ is the majority-carrier correlation energy (CE), being determined by:

$$E_{\text{CE}}(N, r_{\text{d(a)}, X}) \equiv \frac{-0.87553}{0.0908 + r_{\text{sn(sp)}}} + \frac{\frac{0.87553}{0.0908 + r_{\text{sn(sp)}}} + \left(\frac{2[1 - \ln(2)]}{\pi^2} \right) \times \ln(r_{\text{sn(sp)}}) - 0.093288}{1 + 0.03847728 \times r_{\text{sn(sp)}}^{1.67378876}}.$$

So, n(p)-type degenerate X(x)- crystalline alloys, the physical conditions are found to be given by:

$$\frac{k_{\text{Fn(Fp)}}^{-1}}{a_{\text{Bn(Bp)}}} < \frac{\eta_{\text{n(p)}}}{E_{\text{Fno(Fpo)}}} \equiv \frac{1}{A_{\text{n(p)}}} < \frac{k_{\text{Fn(Fp)}}^{-1}}{k_{\text{sn(sp)}}^{-1}} \equiv R_{\text{sn(sp)}}(N, r_{\text{d(a)}, X}) < 1, \\ A_{\text{n(p)}}(N, r_{\text{d(a)}, X}) \equiv \frac{\pm E_{\text{Fno(Fpo)}}}{\eta_{\text{n(p)}}} \quad (15)$$

Here, $\pm E_{\text{Fno(Fpo)}}$ is the Fermi energy at 0 K, and $\eta_{\text{n(p)}}$ is defined in next Eq. (17),

$$\text{as: } \pm E_{\text{Fno(Fpo)}}(N, X) = \frac{\hbar^2 \times k_{\text{Fn(Fp)}}(N, X)^2}{2 \times m_{\text{c(v)}}(X)}, \quad \eta_{\text{n(p)}}(N, r_{\text{d(a)}, X}) = \frac{\sqrt{2\pi N}}{\varepsilon(r_{\text{d(a)}, X})} \times q^2 k_{\text{sn(sp)}}^{-1/2}.$$

Then, the total screened Coulomb impurity potential energy due to the attractive interaction between an electron (hole) charge, $-q(+q)$, at position \vec{r} , and an ionized donor (ionized acceptor) charge: $+q(-q)$ at position \vec{R}_j , randomly distributed throughout X(x)- crystalline alloys, is defined by:

$$V(r) \equiv \sum_{j=1}^N v_j(r) + V_0, \quad (16)$$

where N is the total number of ionized donors (acceptors), V_0 is a constant potential energy, and the screened Coulomb potential energy $v_j(r)$ is defined as:

$$v_j(\mathbf{r}) \equiv -\frac{q^2 \times \exp(-k_{sn(sp)} \times |\vec{r} - \vec{R}_j|)}{\varepsilon(r_{d(a)}) \times |\vec{r} - \vec{R}_j|},$$

where $k_{sn(sp)}$ is the inverse screening length determined in Eq. (12).

Further, using a Fourier transform, the v_j -representation in wave vector \vec{k} -space is given by

$$v_j(\vec{k}) = -\frac{q^2}{\varepsilon(r_{d(a)})} \times \frac{4\pi}{\Omega} \times \frac{1}{k^2 + k_{sn(sp)}^2},$$

where Ω is the total $X(x)$ - crystalline alloy volume.

Then, the effective auto-correlation function for potential fluctuations, $W_{n(p)}(v_{n(p)}, N, r_{d(a)}) \equiv \langle V(r)V(r') \rangle$, was determined, [4, 5] as :

$$W_{n(p)}(v_{n(p)}, N, r_{d(a)}, x) \equiv \eta_{n(p)}^2 \times \exp\left(\frac{-\mathcal{H}_{n(p)} \times R_{sn(sp)}(N, r_{d(a)}, x)}{2\sqrt{|v_{n(p)}|}}\right),$$

$$\eta_{n(p)}(N, r_{d(a)}, x) \equiv \frac{\sqrt{2\pi N}}{\varepsilon(r_{d(a)})} \times q^2 k_{sn(sp)}^{-1/2},$$

$$v_{n(p)}(E, N, x) \equiv \frac{\mp E}{\pm E_{Fno(Fpo)}(N, x)}, \quad \mathcal{H}_{n(p)} = 0.47137. \quad (17)$$

Here, E is the total electron energy, $\varepsilon(r_{d(a)})$ is determined in Equations (8a, 8b), $R_{sn(sp)}(N, r_{d(a)}, x)$ in Eq. (12), and the empirical Heisenberg parameters $\mathcal{H}_{n(p)} = 0.47137$ were chosen above such that the determination of the density of electrons localized in the conduction(valence)-band tails will be accurate, noting that as $E \rightarrow \pm\infty$, $|v_{n(p)}| \rightarrow \infty$, and therefore, $W_{n(p)} \rightarrow \eta_{n(p)}^2$.

In the following, we will calculate the ensemble average of the function: $(E - V)^{a-1/2} \equiv E_k^{a-1/2}$, for $a \geq 1$, $E_k \equiv \frac{\hbar^2 \times k^2}{2 \times m_c(v)(x)}$ being the kinetic energy of the electron (hole), and $V(r)$ determined in Eq. (16), by using the two following integration methods, which strongly depend on $W_{n(p)}(v_{n(p)}, N, r_{d(a)}, x)$.

MATHEMATICAL METHODS

Kane integration method (KIM)

Here, the effective Gaussian distribution probability is defined by:

$$P(V) \equiv \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi W_{n(p)}}} \times \exp\left[\frac{-V^2}{2W_{n(p)}}\right].$$

So, in the Kane integration method, the Gaussian average of $(E - V)^{a-1/2} \equiv E_k^{a-1/2}$ is defined by

$$\langle (E - V)^{a-1/2} \rangle_{KIM} \equiv \langle E_k^{a-1/2} \rangle_{KIM} = \int_{-\infty}^E (E - V)^{a-1/2} \times P(V) dV, \quad \text{for } a \geq 1.$$

Then, by variable changes: $s = (E - V)/\sqrt{W_{n(p)}}$ and $y = \mp E/\sqrt{W_{n(p)}} \equiv \frac{\pm E_{Fno}(Fpo)}{\eta_{n(p)}} \times v_{n(p)} \times \exp\left(\frac{\mathcal{H}_{n(p)} \times R_{sn(sp)}}{4 \times \sqrt{|v_{n(p)}}}\right)$, and using an identity:

$$\int_0^\infty s^{a-\frac{1}{2}} \times \exp(-ys - \frac{s^2}{2}) ds \equiv \Gamma(a + \frac{1}{2}) \times \exp(y^2/4) \times D_{-a-\frac{1}{2}}(y),$$

where $D_{-a-\frac{1}{2}}(y)$ is the parabolic cylinder function and $\Gamma(a + \frac{1}{2})$ is the Gamma function, one thus has:

$$\langle E_k^{a-\frac{1}{2}} \rangle_{KIM} = \frac{\exp(-\frac{y^2}{4}) \times W_{n(p)}^{\frac{2a-1}{4}}}{\sqrt{2\pi}} \times \Gamma(a + \frac{1}{2}) \times D_{-a-\frac{1}{2}}(y) = \frac{\exp(-\frac{y^2}{4}) \times \eta_{n(p)}^{a-\frac{1}{2}}}{\sqrt{2\pi}} \times \exp\left(-\frac{\mathcal{H}_{n(p)} \times R_{sn(sp)} \times (2a-1)}{8 \times \sqrt{|v_{n(p)}}}\right) \times \Gamma(a + \frac{1}{2}) \times D_{-a-\frac{1}{2}}(y). \quad (18)$$

Feynman path-integral method (FPIM)

Here, the ensemble average of $(E - V)^{a-\frac{1}{2}} \equiv E_k^{a-\frac{1}{2}}$ is defined by

$$\langle (E - V)^{a-\frac{1}{2}} \rangle_{FPIM} \equiv \langle E_k^{a-\frac{1}{2}} \rangle_{FPIM} \equiv \frac{\hbar^{a-\frac{1}{2}}}{2^{3/2} \times \sqrt{2\pi}} \times \frac{\Gamma(a+\frac{1}{2})}{\Gamma(\frac{3}{2})} \times \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} (it)^{-a-\frac{1}{2}} \times \exp\left\{\frac{iEt}{\hbar} - \frac{(t\sqrt{W_{n(p)}})^2}{2\hbar^2}\right\} dt, \quad i^2 = -1,$$

noting that as $a=1$, $(it)^{-\frac{3}{2}} \times \exp\left\{-\frac{(t\sqrt{W_{n(p)}})^2}{2\hbar^2}\right\}$ is found to be proportional to the averaged Feynman propagator given the dense donors (acceptors). Then, by variable changes: $t = \frac{\hbar}{\sqrt{W_{n(p)}}}$ and $y =$

$\mp E/\sqrt{W_{n(p)}} \equiv \frac{\pm E_{Fno}(Fpo)}{\eta_{n(p)}} \times v_{n(p)} \times \exp\left(\frac{\mathcal{H}_{n(p)} \times R_{sn(sp)}}{4 \times \sqrt{|v_{n(p)}}}\right)$, for $n(p)$ -type respectively, and then using an identity:

$$\int_{-\infty}^{\infty} (is)^{-a-\frac{1}{2}} \times \exp\left\{iys - \frac{s^2}{2}\right\} ds \equiv 2^{3/2} \times \Gamma(3/2) \times \exp(-y^2/4) \times D_{-a-\frac{1}{2}}(y),$$

one finally obtains: $\langle E_k^{a-\frac{1}{2}} \rangle_{FPIM} \equiv \langle E_k^{a-\frac{1}{2}} \rangle_{KIM}$, $\langle E_k^{a-\frac{1}{2}} \rangle_{KIM}$ being determined in Eq. (18).

In the following, with the use of asymptotic forms for $D_{-a-\frac{1}{2}}(y)$, those given for $\langle (E - V)^{a-\frac{1}{2}} \rangle_{KIM}$ can be obtained in the two following cases.

First case: n-type ($E \geq 0$) and p-type ($E \leq 0$)

As $E \rightarrow \pm\infty$, one has: $v_{n(p)} \rightarrow \mp\infty$ and $y \rightarrow \mp\infty$. In this case, one gets: $D_{-a-\frac{1}{2}}(y \rightarrow \mp\infty) \approx \frac{\sqrt{2\pi}}{\Gamma(a+\frac{1}{2})} \times e^{\frac{y^2}{4}} \times (\mp y)^{a-\frac{1}{2}}$, and therefore from Eq. (18), one gets:

$$\langle E_k^{a-\frac{1}{2}} \rangle_{KIM} \approx E^{a-\frac{1}{2}}.$$

Further, as $E \rightarrow \pm 0$, one has: $v_{n(p)} \rightarrow \mp 0$ and $y \rightarrow \mp 0$. So, one obtains:

$$D_{-a-\frac{1}{2}}(y \rightarrow \mp 0) \approx \beta(a) \times \exp\left(\left(\sqrt{a} + \frac{1}{16a^2}\right)y - \frac{y^2}{16a} + \frac{y^3}{24\sqrt{a}}\right) \rightarrow \beta(a), \quad \beta(a) = \frac{\sqrt{\pi}}{2^{\frac{2a+1}{4}} \Gamma(\frac{a+3}{4})}.$$

Therefore, as $E \rightarrow \pm 0$, from Eq. (18), one gets: $\langle E_k^{a-\frac{1}{2}} \rangle_{KIM} \rightarrow 0$.

Thus, in this case, one gets:

$$\langle E_k^{a-\frac{1}{2}} \rangle_{KIM} \cong E^{a-\frac{1}{2}}. \quad (19)$$

Second case: n-type-case ($E \leq 0$) and p-type-case ($E \geq 0$)

As $E \rightarrow \mp 0$, one has: $(y, v_{n(p)}) \rightarrow \pm 0$, and by putting $f(a) \equiv \frac{\eta_{n(p)}^{a-\frac{1}{2}}}{\sqrt{2\pi}} \times \Gamma(a + \frac{1}{2}) \times \beta(a)$, Eq. (18) yields:

$$\begin{aligned} H_{n(p)}(v_{n(p)} \rightarrow \pm 0, N, r_{d(a)}, x, a) &= \frac{\langle E_k^{a-\frac{1}{2}} \rangle_{KIM}}{f(a)} = \\ &= \exp\left[-\frac{\mathcal{H}_{n(p)} \times R_{sn(sp)} \times (2a-1)}{8 \times \sqrt{|v_{n(p)}|}} - \left(\sqrt{a} + \frac{1}{16a^2}\right)y - \left(\frac{1}{4} + \frac{1}{16a}\right)y^2 - \frac{y^3}{24\sqrt{a}}\right] \rightarrow 0. \end{aligned} \quad (20)$$

Further, as $E \rightarrow \mp \infty$, one has: $(y, v_{n(p)}) \rightarrow \pm \infty$. Thus, one gets: $D_{-a-\frac{1}{2}}(y \rightarrow \pm \infty) \approx y^{-a-\frac{1}{2}} \times e^{-\frac{y^2}{4}} \rightarrow 0$.

Therefore, from Eq. (18), one gets:

$$\begin{aligned} K_{n(p)}(v_{n(p)} \rightarrow \pm \infty, N, r_{d(a)}, x, a) &\equiv \frac{\langle E_k^{a-\frac{1}{2}} \rangle_{KIM}}{f(a)} \approx \frac{1}{\beta(a)} \times \exp\left(-\frac{(A_{n(p)} \times v_{n(p)})^2}{2}\right) \times \\ &\times (A_{n(p)} \times v_{n(p)})^{-a-\frac{1}{2}} \rightarrow 0, \end{aligned} \quad (21)$$

noting that $\beta(a) = \frac{\sqrt{\pi}}{2^{\frac{2a+1}{4}} \Gamma(\frac{a+3}{4})}$, being equal to: $\frac{\sqrt{\pi}}{2^{\frac{3}{4}} \times \Gamma(5/4)}$ for $a=1$, and $\frac{\sqrt{\pi}}{2^{3/2}}$ for $a = 5/2$.

It should be noted that those ratios: $\frac{\langle E_k^{a-\frac{1}{2}} \rangle_{KIM}}{f(a)}$, obtained in Equations (20) and (21), can be taken in an approximate form as:

$$F_{n(p)}(v_{n(p)}, N, r_{d(a)}, x, a) = K_{n(p)}(v_{n(p)}, N, r_{d(a)}, x, a) + [H_{n(p)}(v_{n(p)}, N, r_{d(a)}, x, a) - K_{n(p)}(v_{n(p)}, N, r_{d(a)}, x, a)] \times \exp[-c_1 \times (A_{n(p)} v_{n(p)})^{c_2}], \quad (22)$$

so that: $F_{n(p)}(v_{n(p)}, N, r_{d(a)}, x, a) \rightarrow H_{n(p)}(v_{n(p)}, N, r_{d(a)}, x, a)$ for $0 \leq v_n \leq 16$, and $F_{n(p)}(v_{n(p)}, N, r_{d(a)}, x, a) \rightarrow K_{n(p)}(v_{n(p)}, N, r_{d(a)}, x, a)$ for $v_{n(p)} \geq 16$. Here, the constants c_1 and c_2 may be respectively chosen as: $c_1 = 10^{-40}$ and $c_2 = 80$, as $a = 1$, being used to determine the critical density of electrons (holes) localized in the exponential conduction(valence) band-tails (EBT), $N_{CDn(CDp)}^{EBT}(N, r_{d(a)}, x)$, given in the following.

$N_{CDn(CDp)}^{EBT}(N, r_{d(a)}, x)$ -formular

Here, by using Eq. (18) for $a=1$, the density of states $\mathcal{D}(E)$ is defined by:

$$\langle \mathcal{D}(E_k) \rangle_{KIM} \equiv \frac{g_c(v)}{2\pi^2} \left(\frac{2m_c(v)}{\hbar^2} \right)^{\frac{3}{2}} \times \langle E_k^{\frac{1}{2}} \rangle_{KIM} = \frac{g_c(v)}{2\pi^2} \left(\frac{2m_c(v)}{\hbar^2} \right)^{\frac{3}{2}} \times \frac{\exp\left(-\frac{y^2}{4}\right) \times W_n^{\frac{1}{4}}}{\sqrt{2\pi}} \times \Gamma\left(\frac{3}{2}\right) \times D_{-\frac{3}{2}}(y) = \mathcal{D}(E). \quad (23)$$

Going back to the functions: H_n , K_n and F_n , given respectively in Equations (20-22), in which the factor $\frac{\langle E_k^{\frac{1}{2}} \rangle_{KIM}}{f(a=1)}$ is now replaced by:

$$\frac{\langle E_k^{\frac{1}{2}} \rangle_{KIM}}{f(a=1)} = \frac{\mathcal{D}(E \leq 0)}{\mathcal{D}_0} = F_{n(p)}(v_{n(p)}, N, r_{d(a)}, x, a = 1), \quad \mathcal{D}_0(N, r_{d(a)}, x, a = 1) = \frac{g_c(v) \times (m_c(v) \times m_0)^{3/2} \times \sqrt{\eta_{n(p)}}}{2\pi^2 \hbar^3} \times \beta(a),$$

$$\beta(a = 1) = \frac{\sqrt{\pi}}{2^{\frac{3}{2}} \times \Gamma(5/4)}. \quad (24)$$

Therefore, $N_{CDn(CDp)}^{EBT}(N, r_{d(a)}, x)$ can be defined by: $N_{CDn(CDp)}^{EBT}(N, r_{d(a)}, x) = \int_{-\infty}^0 \mathcal{D}(E \leq 0) dE$,

$$N_{CDn(CDp)}^{EBT}(N, r_{d(a)}, x) = \frac{g_c(v) \times (m_c(v))^{\frac{3}{2}} \sqrt{\eta_{n(p)}} \times (\pm \mathbf{E}_{Fno}(\mathbf{Fpo}))}{2\pi^2 \hbar^3} \times \left\{ \int_0^{16} \beta(a = 1) \times F_{n(p)}(v_{n(p)}, N, r_{d(a)}, x, a = 1) dv_{n(p)} + I_{n(p)} \right\}, \quad (25)$$

where

$$I_{n(p)} \equiv \int_{16}^{\infty} \beta(a = 1) \times K_{n(p)}(v_{n(p)}, N, r_{d(a)}, x, a = 1) dv_{n(p)} = \int_{16}^{\infty} e^{-\frac{(A_{n(p)} \times v_{n(p)})^2}{2}} \times (A_{n(p)} v_{n(p)})^{-3/2} dv_{n(p)}.$$

Then, by another variable change: $t = [A_{n(p)} v_{n(p)} / \sqrt{2}]^2$, the integral $I_{n(p)}$ yields:

$I_{n(p)} = \frac{1}{2^{5/4} A_{n(p)}} \times \int_{z_{n(p)}}^{\infty} t^{b-1} e^{-t} dt \equiv \frac{\Gamma(b, z_{n(p)})}{2^{5/4} \times A_{n(p)}}$, where $b = -1/4$, $z_{n(p)} = [16A_{n(p)}/\sqrt{2}]^2$, and $\Gamma(b, z_{n(p)})$ is the incomplete Gamma function, defined by: $\Gamma(b, z_{n(p)}) \simeq z_{n(p)}^{b-1} \times e^{-z_{n(p)}} \left[1 + \sum_{j=1}^{16} \frac{(b-1)(b-2)\dots(b-j)}{z_{n(p)}^j} \right]$.

Finally, Eq. (25) now yields:

$$N_{CDn(CDp)}^{EBT} [N = N_{CDn(NDp)}(r_{d(a)}, x), r_{d(a)}, x] = \frac{g_{c(v)} \times (m_{c(v)})^{\frac{3}{2}} \sqrt{\eta_{n(p)}} \times (\pm E_{Fno}(F_{po}))}{2\pi^2 \hbar^3} \times \left\{ \int_0^{16} \beta(a=1) \times F_{n(p)}(v_{n(p)}, N, r_{d(a)}, x, a=1) dv_{n(p)} + \frac{\Gamma(b, z_{n(p)})}{2^{5/4} \times A_{n(p)}} \right\}, \quad (26)$$

being the density of electrons (holes) localized in the EBT, respectively.

In $n(p)$ -type degenerate $X(x)$ - crystalline alloys, the numerical results of $N_{CDn(CDp)}^{EBT} [N = N_{CDn(NDp)}(r_{d(a)}, x), r_{d(a)}, x] \equiv N_{CDn(CDp)}^{EBT}(r_{d(a)}, x)$, for a simplicity of presentation, evaluated using Eq. (26), are given in following Tables 1, 2, 3 in Appendix 1, in which those of other functions such as: $B_{do(ao)}$, ε , $E_{gno(gp_o)}$, and $N_{CDn(CDp)}$ are computed, using Equations (6), (8a), (8b), and (10), respectively, noting that the relative deviations in absolute values are defined by: $|RD| \equiv \left| 1 - \frac{N_{CDn(CDp)}^{EBT}}{N_{CDn(CDp)}} \right|$.

Tables 1, 2, 3 in Appendix 1.

CONCLUSION

In those Tables 1, 2, 3, some concluding remarks are given and discussed in the following.

(1)-For a given x , while $\varepsilon(r_{d(a)}, x)$ decreases (\searrow), the functions: $E_{gno(gp_o)}(r_{d(a)}, x)$, $N_{CDn(CDp)}(r_{d(a)}, x)$ and $N_{CDn(CDp)}^{EBT}(r_{d(a)}, x)$ increase (\nearrow), with increasing (\nearrow) $r_{d(a)}$, due to the impurity size effect.

(2)-Further, for a given $r_{d(a)}$, while $\varepsilon(r_{d(a)}, x)$ also decreases (\searrow), the functions: $E_{gno(gp_o)}(r_{d(a)}, x)$, $N_{CDn(CDp)}(r_{d(a)}, x)$ and $N_{CDn(CDp)}^{EBT}(r_{d(a)}, x)$ also increase (\nearrow), with increasing (\nearrow) x .

(3)- In those Tables 1, 2 and 3, one notes that the maximal value of $|RD|$ is found to be given by: 2.92×10^{-7} , meaning that $N_{CDn}^{EBT} \cong N_{CDn}$. In other words, such the critical $d(a)$ -density $N_{CDn(NDp)}(r_{d(a)}, x)$, is just the density of electrons (holes) localized in the EBT, $N_{CDn(CDp)}^{EBT}(r_{d(a)}, x)$, respectively.

(4) Finally, once $N_{CDn(CDp)}$ is determined, the effective density of free electrons (holes), N^* , given in the parabolic conduction (valence) band of the $n(p)$ -type degenerate $X(x)$ - crystalline alloy, can thus be defined by:

$$N^*(N, r_{d(a)}, x) \equiv N - N_{CDn(NDp)} \cong N - N_{CDn(CDp)}^{EBT},$$

needing to determine the optical, electrical, and thermoelectric properties in such $n(p)$ -type degenerate $X(x)$ -crystalline alloys, as those studied in $n(p)$ -type degenerate crystals [4, 5, 9, 10, 11].

REFERENCES

1. H. Van Cong, "Maximal Efficiencies investigated in New Single $n^+(p^+) - p(n)$ GaAs_{1-x}Te_x- Alloy Junction Solar Cells at 300 K, $0 \leq x \leq 1$, According to Highest Hot Reservoir Temperatures, $T_H(K) = 447$ (465.5), obtained respectively from Carnot-Efficiency Theorem, being proved by Entropy Law", *Eur. J. Theor. Appl. Sci.*, vol. 2, pp. 54-74, 2024. DOI: 10.59324/ejtas.2024.2(1).04
2. H. Van Cong, "Maximal Efficiencies in New Single GaAs_{1-x}Sb_x- Alloy Junction Solar Cells at 300K", *European Journal of Theoretical and Applied Sciences*, vol. 2, pp. 394-414, 2024. DOI: 10.59324/ejtas.2024.2(1).34
3. H. Van Cong, "Maximal Efficiencies in New Single GaAs_{1-x}P_x- Alloy Junction Solar Cells at 300 K", *Eur. J. Theor. Appl. Sci.*, vol. 2, pp. 75-95, 2024. DOI: 10.59324/ejtas.2024.2(1).05
4. H. Van Cong, "Same maximum figure of merit $ZT(=1)$, due to effects of impurity size and heavy doping, obtained in n(p)-type degenerate GaAs-crystal, at same reduced Fermi energy and same minimum (maximum) Seebeck coefficient, at which same Mott $ZT(=1)$ ", *SCIREA J. Phys.*, vol. 8, pp. 133-157, 2023. DOI: 10.54647/physics140532
5. H. Van Cong, "Accurate expressions of the optical coefficients, given in n(p)-type degenerate GaAs-crystals, due to the impurity-size effect, and obtained by an improved Forouhi-Bloomer parameterization model (FB-PM)", *SCIREA J. Phys.*, vol. 8, pp. 172-197, 2023. DOI: 10.54647/physics140552
6. M.A. Green et al., "Solar cell efficiency tables (version 60)", *Prog. Photovolt. Res. & Appl.*, vol. 30, pp. 687-701, 2022. DOI: 10.1002/pip.3595
7. C. Kittel, "Introduction to Solid State Physics", Wiley, New York, pp. 84-100, 1976.
8. S. Moon et al., "Highly efficient single GaAs thin-film solar cell on flexible substrate", *Sci. Rep.*, vol. 6, p. 30107, 2016. DOI: 10.1038/srep30107
9. H. Van Cong et al., "Optical bandgap in various impurity-Si systems from the metal-insulator transition study", *Physica B*, vol. 436, pp. 130-139, 2014. DOI: 10.1016/J.PHYSB.2013.11.041
10. H. Van Cong & G. Debiais, "A simple accurate expression of the reduced Fermi energy for any reduced carrier density", *J. Appl. Phys.*, vol. 73, pp. 1545-1546, 1993. DOI: 10.1063/1.353232
11. H. Van Cong et al., "Size effect on different impurity levels in semiconductors", *Solid State Communications*, vol. 49, pp. 697-699, 1984. DOI: 10.1016/0038-1098(84)90223-0

APPENDIX 1

Table 1. In the GaAs_{1-x}Te_x-alloy the numerical results of $B_{do(ao)}$, ϵ , $E_{gno(gp)}$, $N_{CDn(CDp)}$, and $N_{CDn(CDp)}^{EBT}$ are computed, using Equations (6), (8a), (8b), (10), and (26), respectively, noting that the relative deviations in absolute values are defined by: $|RD| \equiv \left| 1 - \frac{N_{CDn(CDp)}^{EBT}}{N_{CDn(CDp)}} \right|$, giving rise to their maximal value equal to 2.89×10^{-7} , meaning that such the critical d(a)-density $N_{CDn(NDp)}(r_{d(a)}, x)$, determined in Eq. (10) is just the density of electrons (holes) localized in the EBT, $N_{CDn(CDp)}^{EBT}(r_{d(a)}, x)$, determined in Eq. (26), respectively. Here, on notes that in the limiting conditions: $x=0, 1$, these results are reduced to those given in GaAs-and-GaTe crystals, respectively.

Donor		P			AS			Te		
r_d (nm)	↗	0.110			$r_{do}=0.118$			0.132		
x	↗	0	0.5	1	0	0.5	1	0	0.5	1
$B_{do}(x)$ in 10^8 (N/m ²)	↗				1.211940	2.692382	4.3732354			
$\epsilon(r_d, x)$	↘	13.40073	12.97718	12.553622	13.13	12.715	12.3	12.327231	11.93760	11.547977
$E_{gno}(r_d, x)$ eV	↗	1.519792	1.657537	1.7952485	1.52	1.658	1.796	1.5207002	1.659555	1.7985267
$N_{CDn}(r_d, x)$ in 10^{16} cm ⁻³	↗	1.253837	12.484254	48.431412	1.3330088	13.27255	51.489527	1.6107592	16.03807	62.218067
$N_{CDn}^{EBT}(r_d, x)$ in 10^{16} cm ⁻³	↗	1.2538371	12.484251	48.431399	1.3330084	13.272547	51.489513	1.6107588	16.038061	62.218050
RD in 10^{-7}		2.89	2.45	2.68	2.87	2.62	2.74	2.69	2.83	2.70
Donor		Sb			Sn					
r_d (nm)	↗	0.136			0.140					
x	↗	0	0.5	1	0	0.5	1			
$\epsilon(r_d, x)$	↘	11.857485	11.48270	11.107926	11.327101	10.96908	10.611069			
$E_{gno}(r_d, x)$ eV	↗	1.5211775	1.660616	1.8002489	1.5217893	1.661975	1.8024567			
$N_{CDn}(r_d, x)$ in 10^{16} cm ⁻³	↗	1.8098785	18.02066	69.909357	2.0762080	20.67246	80.196749			
$N_{CDn}^{EBT}(r_d, x)$ in 10^{16} cm ⁻³	↗	1.8098780	18.020659	69.909340	2.0762075	20.672458	80.196728			
RD in 10^{-7}		2.87	2.84	2.64	2.51	2.75	2.63			
Acceptor		B			Ga			Mg		
r_a (nm)	↗	0.088			$r_{ao}=0.126$			0.140		

x	↗	0	0.5	1	0	0.5	1	0	0.5	1
$B_{ao}(x)$ in 10^8 (N/m ²)	↗				4.388991	5.556694	6.874656			
$\epsilon(r_a, x)$	↘	24.3813	23.61066	22.8400	13.13	12.715	12.3	12.42055	12.0279	11.6354
$E_{gpo}(r_a, x)$ eV	↗	1.50370	1.637365	1.77047	1.52	1.658	1.796	1.5226974	1.66111	1.80022
$N_{CDp}(r_a, x)$ in 10^{18} cm ⁻³	↗	0.178445	0.3288630	0.5637475	1.142563	2.105671	3.6096078	1.3497457	2.487495	4.264143
$N_{CDp}^{EBT}(r_a, x)$ in 10^{18} cm ⁻³	↗	0.1784451	0.3288629	0.5637474	1.1425627	2.105670	3.6096068	1.3497453	2.4874943	4.264142
$ RD $ in 10^{-7}		2.75	2.72	2.71	2.59	2.65	2.72	2.82	2.67	2.75
Acceptor		In			Cd					
r_a (nm)	↗	0.144			0.148					
x	↗	0	0.5	1	0	0.5	1			
$\epsilon(r_a, x)$	↘	11.999115	11.6198	11.24060	11.51747	11.15344	10.78941			
$E_{gpo}(r_a, x)$ eV	↗	1.5245311	1.66374	1.803097	1.526878	1.666708	1.806773			
$N_{CDp}(r_a, x)$ in 10^{18} cm ⁻³	↗	1.4970169	2.7589064	4.7294055	1.6927886	3.1197012	5.3478913			
$N_{CDp}^{EBT}(r_a, x)$ in 10^{18} cm ⁻³	↗	1.4970165	2.7589057	4.7294042	1.6927881	3.1197004	5.3478899			
$ RD $ in 10^{-7}		2.81	2.69	2.81	2.74	2.68	2.67			

Table 2. In the GaAs_{1-x}Sb_x-alloy the numerical results of $B_{do(ao)}$, ϵ , $E_{gno(gp)}$, $N_{CDn(CDp)}$, and $N_{CDn(CDp)}^{EBT}$ are computed, using Equations (6), (8a), (8b), (10), and (26), respectively, noting that the relative deviations in absolute values are defined by: $|RD| \equiv \left| 1 - \frac{N_{CDn(CDp)}^{EBT}}{N_{CDn(CDp)}} \right|$, giving rise to their maximal value equal to 2.90×10^{-7} , meaning that such the critical d(a)-density $N_{CDn(NDp)}(r_{d(a)}, x)$, determined in Eq. (10) is just the density of electrons (holes) localized in the EBT, $N_{CDn(CDp)}^{EBT}(r_{d(a)}, x)$, determined in Eq. (26), respectively. Here, on notes that in the limiting conditions: $x=0, 1$, these results are reduced to those given in GaAs-and-GaSb crystals, respectively.

Donor		P			As			Te		
r_d (nm)	↗	0.110			$r_{do}=0.118$			0.132		
x	↗	0	0.5	1	0	0.5	1	0	0.5	1
$B_{do}(x)$ in 10^8 (N/m ²)	↘				1.211940	0.861365	0.6043921			

$\epsilon(r_d, x)$	↗	13.40073	14.707129	16.013522	13.13	14.41	15.69	12.32723	13.52897	14.730712
$E_{gno}(r_d, x)$ eV	↗	1.519792	1.164852	0.8098961	1.52	1.165	0.81	1.520700	1.165498	0.8103492
$N_{CDn}(r_d, x)$ in 10^{16} cm^{-3}	↗	1.253837	0.5950549	0.2653557	1.3330088	0.6326285	0.2821111	1.6107592	0.764445	0.3408927
$N_{CDn}^{EBT}(r_d, x)$ in 10^{16} cm^{-3}	↗	1.2538371	0.5950547	0.2653556	1.3330084	0.6326284	0.2821110	1.6107588	0.7644451	0.3408926
$ RD $ in 10^{-7}		2.89	2.70	2.77	2.87	2.66	2.62	2.69	2.70	2.80
Donor		Sb			Sn					
r_d (nm)	↗	0.136			0.140					
x	↗	0	0.5	1	0	0.5	1			
$\epsilon(r_d, x)$	↘	11.857485	13.01343	14.169379	11.327101	12.43134	13.535584			
$E_{gno}(r_d, x)$ eV	↗	1.5211775	1.165837	0.8105872	1.5217893	1.166272	0.8108923			
$N_{CDn}(r_d, x)$ in 10^{16} cm^{-3}	↗	1.8098785	0.858945	0.3830333	2.0762080	0.9853412	0.4393979			
$N_{CDn}^{EBT}(r_d, x)$ in 10^{16} cm^{-3}	↗	1.8098780	0.8589444	0.3830332	2.0762075	0.98534094	0.4393978			
$ RD $ in 10^{-7}		2.87	2.65	2.63	2.51	2.68	2.75			
Acceptor		B			Ga			Mg		
r_a (nm)	↗	0.088			$r_{ao}=0.126$			0.140		
x	↗	0	0.5	1	0	0.5	1	0	0.5	1
$B_{ao}(x)$ in $10^8 \text{ (N/m}^2)$	↘				4.388991	3.7002469	3.1686667			
$\epsilon(r_a, x)$	↘	24.3813	26.75813	29.13498	13.13	14.41	15.69	12.42055	13.63139	14.84222
$E_{gpo}(r_a, x)$ eV	↗	1.50370	1.151259	0.798233	1.52	1.165	0.81	1.5226974	1.167274	0.8119474
$N_{CDp}(r_a, x)$ in 10^{18} cm^{-3}	↗	0.178445	0.1413515	0.1145816	1.142563	0.90505691	0.7336523	1.3497457	1.069172	0.86668661
$N_{CDp}^{EBT}(r_a, x)$ in 10^{18} cm^{-3}	↗	0.1784451	0.14135149	0.1145816	1.1425627	0.9050567	0.7336521	1.3497453	1.0691719	0.86668638
$ RD $ in 10^{-7}	↗	2.75	2.70	2.49	2.59	2.70	2.72	2.82	2.55	2.67
Acceptor		In			Cd					
r_a (nm)	↗	0.144			0.148					
x	↗	0	0.5	1	0	0.5	1			
$\epsilon(r_a, x)$	↘	11.999115	13.1689	14.33862	11.51747	12.64027	13.763073			

$E_{gpo}(r_a, x)$ eV	↗	1.5245311	1.16882	0.813271	1.526878	1.170799	0.8149657
$N_{CDp}(r_a, x)$ in 10^{18} cm^{-3}	↗	1.4970169	1.1858300	0.96125108	1.6927886	1.3409063	1.0869583
$N_{CDp}^{EBT}(r_a, x)$ in 10^{18} cm^{-3}	↗	1.4970165	1.1858297	0.96125083	1.6927881	1.3409060	1.0869580
$ RD $ in 10^{-7}		2.81	2.90	2.81	2.74	2.46	2.87

Table 3. In the $\text{GaAs}_{1-x}\text{P}_x$ -alloy the numerical results of $B_{do(ao)}$, ϵ , $E_{gno(gp)}$, $N_{CDn(CDp)}$, and $N_{CDn(CDp)}^{EBT}$ are computed, using Equations (6), (8a), (8b), (10), and (26), respectively, noting that the relative deviations in absolute values are defined by: $|RD| \equiv \left| 1 - \frac{N_{CDn(CDp)}^{EBT}}{N_{CDn(CDp)}} \right|$, giving rise to their maximal value equal to 2.92×10^{-7} , meaning that such the critical d(a)-density $N_{CDn(NDp)}(r_{d(a)}, x)$, determined in Eq. (10) is just the density of electrons (holes) localized in the EBT, $N_{CDn(CDp)}^{EBT}(r_{d(a)}, x)$, determined in Eq. (26), respectively. Here, on notes that in the limiting conditions: $x=0, 1$, these results are reduced to those given in GaAs-and-GaP crystals, respectively.

Donor		P			As			Te		
r_d (nm)	↗	0.110			$r_{do}=0.118$			0.132		
x	↗	0	0.5	1	0	0.5	1	0	0.5	1
$B_{do}(x)$ in $10^8 \text{ (N/m}^2\text{)}$	↗				1.211940	2.113713	3.340137			
$\epsilon(r_d, x)$	↘	13.40073	12.36481	11.328878	13.13	12.115	11.1	12.32723	11.374288	10.421345
$E_{gno}(r_d, x)$ eV	↗	1.519792	1.65574	1.7954260	1.52	1.658	1.796	1.520700	1.659221	1.797930
$N_{CDn}(r_d, x)$ in 10^{16} cm^{-3}	↗	1.253837	5.2253042	15.858596	1.3330088	5.5552466	16.859958	1.6107592	6.7127576	20.372959
$N_{CDn}^{EBT}(r_d, x)$ in 10^{16} cm^{-3}	↗	1.2538371	5.2253028	15.858592	1.3330084	5.5552451	16.859954	1.6107588	6.7127558	20.372954
$ RD $ in 10^{-7}		2.89	2.73	2.74	2.87	2.64	2.60	2.69	2.72	2.69
Donor		Sb			Sn					
r_d (nm)	↗	0.136			0.140					
x	↗	0	0.5	1	0	0.5	1			
$\epsilon(r_d, x)$	↘	11.857485	10.94085	10.024226	11.327101	10.45147	9.5758431			
$E_{gno}(r_d, x)$ eV	↗	1.5211775	1.660054	1.7992452	1.5217893	1.661121	1.8009315			
$N_{CDn}(r_d, x)$ in 10^{16} cm^{-3}	↗	1.8098785	7.542577	22.891429	2.0762080	8.6524921	26.259978			

N_{CDn}^{EBT} in 10^{16} cm^{-3}	↗	1.8098780	7.542575	22.891423	2.0762075	8.6524898	26.259971			
RD in 10^{-7}		2.87	2.65	2.80	2.51	2.61	2.57			
Acceptor		B			Ga			Mg		
r_a (nm)	↗	0.088			$r_{ao}=0.126$			0.140		
x	↗	0	0.5	1	0	0.5	1	0	0.5	1
$B_{ao}(x)$ in $10^8 \text{ (N/m}^2)$	↗				4.388991	7.0064952	10.55177			
$\epsilon(r_a, x)$	↘	24.3813	22.496513	20.61174	13.13	12.115	11.1	12.42055	11.46039	10.500236
$E_{gpo}(r_a, x)$ eV	↗	1.50370	1.1631981	0.756815	1.52	1.658	1.796	1.5226974	1.662306	1.802485
$N_{CDp}(r_a, x)$ in 10^{18} cm^{-3}	↗	0.178445	0.5702814	1.4981699	1.142563	3.6514435	9.592603	1.3497457	4.3135651	11.332043
$N_{CDp}^{EBT}(r_a, x)$ in 10^{18} cm^{-3}	↗	0.1784451	0.5702813	1.4981695	1.1425627	3.6514425	9.592600	1.3497453	4.3135640	11.332040
RD in 10^{-7}		2.75	2.63	2.52	2.59	2.702	2.71	2.82	2.61	2.44
Acceptor		In			Cd					
r_a (nm)	↗	0.144			0.148					
x	↗	0	0.5	1	0	0.5	1			
$\epsilon(r_a, x)$	↘	11.999115	11.07154	10.14396	11.51747	10.62713	9.7367823			
$E_{gpo}(r_a, x)$ eV	↗	1.5245311	1.665233	1.806893	1.526878	1.668980	1.8125359			
$N_{CDp}(r_a, x)$ in 10^{18} cm^{-3}	↗	1.4970169	4.7842197	12.5684870	1.6927886	5.4098739	14.2121250			
$N_{CDp}^{EBT}(r_a, x)$ in 10^{18} cm^{-3}	↗	1.4970165	4.7842184	12.5684830	1.6927881	5.4098724	14.2121210			
RD in 10^{-7}		2.81	2.70	2.92	2.74	2.71	2.84			

